

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

EU4CHILD is an EU-funded project with a clear goal: map the current landscape of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications for Childhood Cancer to understand how AI can help improve care pathways in the EU

The facts

Why Childhood Cancer?

Childhood Cancer represents the leading cause of death from disease for children and adolescents in Europe –accounting for 20% of deaths after infancy– and is a major contributor to morbidity in survivors.

Our tools

What is Artificial Intelligence?

By AI we mean **computer systems** that can perform tasks normally requiring **human intelligence**: visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, pattern recognition, automatic translation

A knowledge base for Childhood Cancer

A **one-stop portal** to host and curate **resources** and **insights** on Childhood Cancer and liaise future opportunities to expand the reach and uptake of **clinical AI applications**

Bringing together clinicians, young cancer patients and AI experts

We seek to connect **key European stakeholders** in Childhood Cancer to facilitate their interaction and cooperation

Our ambition

Shining a light on Childhood Cancer

We aim to harness the **power of AI** and **real-world data** into meaningful applications that can be integrated in the clinical practice to transform the way we **diagnose, treat** and **care** for children and adolescents living with cancer.

Ensuring equal access to cancer diagnosis and treatment across Europe

Fostering a sustainable, ethical & digital transformation for healthcare in Europe

Improving outcomes & quality of life and for young survivors

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EU4CHILD receives funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783